

Book Title Scanner Using Tesseract OCR

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Abstract — Optical Character Recognition (OCR) allows the system to identify the scripts or alphabets written into users' verbal communication, without human intervention. OCR has become an individual from the predominantly thriving application of knowledge in the area of artificial intelligence and pattern detection. The accuracy of OCR can be dependent on certain factors like pre-processing and segmentation algorithms. Retrieving text from the image can be difficult because of the difference in style, complex background of the image, orientation, size, etc. This study begins with an introduction to the optical character recognition (OCR) technique, Tesseract's architecture, and the experiment's findings about OCR using Tesseract on various types of book covers.

Keywords— Optical Character Recognition, OCR, Pre-processing stages, Text Recognition, Gray Scale, Adaptive Threshold.

I. INTRODUCTION

Optical character recognition, or OCR, turns scanned information into fully searchable documents from images with text that computers can recognise. Instead of the conventional method of manually transcribing the text, OCR gathers pertinent information and automatically adds it to the digital database. An ASCII character that a computer can recognise is created by OCR from a printed document or scanned page. The written text in the file image may be typewritten, handwritten, or both.

In the scanning step of OCR, we use a high-resolution picture of the book cover page, and read it using Python OpenCV. In order to validate the recognition process, characters from the page and parallel machine-editable ASCII characters are employed along with a number of sophisticated algorithms, previously loaded templates, and dictionaries. The font and size make recognition difficult if pre-processing, feature extraction, and recognition are not strong. Noisy pixels may occur which are familiarised due to the image scanning. So, stroke width can affect recognition to an extent. In order to get good character recognition, one must first receive binary image data, eliminate noise, smooth the image for enhanced recognition, effectively extract functions, train the system, and classify the patterns.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Together with Handel, Gustav Tauschek got an OCR patent in Germany in 1929. Handel later acquired an OCR patent in the US in 1933. In 1935 Tauschek become additionally provided A US patent for his technique. 2533 global magazine of Engineering research & generation (IJERT) St. three quantity 2, February - 2014 IJERT ISSN: 2278-0181 IJERTV3IS21393 www.ijert.org RCA engineers had been operating on the first primitive in 1949 pc-kind OCR to assist the blind within the US Veterans administration, however in place of changing revealed characters into gadget language, the equipment he transformed them into system language and then reported the letters. It grew to become out to be too pricey and become now not followed up on after checking out [1] [2].

Valley sharpening techniques that limit the histogram to pixels with large absolute values of derivatives, such as S. Watanabe, and others, are recommended against by Khankasikam et al [10], [4]. Al [2, 8] suggested using a histogram distinction strategy to choose a gray-level threshold with the greatest amount of difference. This method modifies the histogram to make it usable for thresholding by using information about nearby pixels or edges inside the original picture. By applying least-manner tactics and statistical selection-making techniques, the size of the histogram of the Gaussian distribution is estimated [2]. Those methods are tedious and call for excessive computational power.

The notion of using both intensities and geographical facts was considered in Di Ges [9], [2], since they account for the neighbourhood information used in human belief. AND a great deal of novel approaches and strategies have been developed and put forth in the recent years to locate global I neighbourhood solutions in a nonlinear multimodal feature optimization [9], [6]. Additionally, there have been tests conducted on artificial neural networks and fuzzy common sense

for optical person detection. Multiple vertices can be kept inside the multimodal optimization hassle with the use of clustering. The clustering method is incredibly accurate in detecting the tops in bimodal histograms.

III. ARCHITECTURE OF TESSERACT

Fig. 1. Architecture of Tesseract OCR

As seen in fig. 1, Tesseract OCR's operation is straightforward and simple to understand. Adaptive thresholding is the first step [2]. A picture is converted into binary images in this step. Character outlines are then extracted using linked component analysis. Tesseract OCR, which performs OCR of images with white text and black backgrounds, is likely the first to offer this technique and is quite helpful. Then, Blobs are created from these outlines. Using definite and fuzzy spaces, text is divided into words [2]. The two processes of text recognition are launched as shown in fig 1. During the initial pass, each word from the text will be recognised. An adaptive classifier receives training data for each word factory. [2].

The classifier will identify text accurately. The final phase resolves various issues and extract text from images. Each phase is explained in detail at [2].

IV. METHODOLOGY

i. Gray Scale the image

Gray scaling converts the image from other color spaces like RGB, CMYK, HSV, etc. to shades of

gray. It adjusts between complete black and complete white.

Gray scaling is done for the following reasons:

- *Dimension reduction:* RGB images usually have three dimensions whereas gray-scaled images only have one dimension.
- *Reduces model complexity:* The three-dimensional images usually have like 300 input nodes whereas the same neutral network of a gray-scaled image has only 100 inputs.
- *For other algorithms to work:* Algorithms like Canny edge of OpenCV library only work with Grayscale images.

ii. Adaptive Thresholding

In simple thresholding, each pixel in the image has the same threshold value since the threshold has a global value. The threshold value of smaller regions is assessed and therefore, threshold values will be unique for different regions in adaptive thresholding.

[adaptiveThreshold\(src, dst, maxValue, adaptiveMethod, thresholdType, blockSize, C\)](#)

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The steps involved in building the model are:

- Import the necessary packages

```
import pytesseract
import cv2
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

- Import tesseract-ocr application

```
pytesseract.pytesseract.tesseract=r"C:\Program Files\Tesseract-OCR\tesseract.exe"
```

- Read and resize the image

```
img = cv2.imread('kite.jpg')
```

```
img = cv2.resize(img, None, fx=0.5, fy=0.5)
```


iv. Noise Removal

```
#noise removal
img = cv2.fastNlMeansDenoisingColored(img, None, 10, 10, 7, 15)
```

v. Gray scale the image and display the result

```
gray = cv2.cvtColor(img, cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
```



```
img2Char = pytesseract.image_to_string(gray)
img2Char = ' '.join(img2Char.splitlines())
print(img2Char)
```

KHALED HOSSEINI THE KITE RUNNER

vi. Adaptive threshold the image for better accuracy and display the results

```
adaptive_threshold = cv2.adaptiveThreshold(gray, 255, cv2.ADAPTIVE_THRESH_GAUSSIAN_C, cv2.THRESH_BINARY, 113, 11)
```

```
adaptive_threshold = cv2.adaptiveThreshold(gray,
255,cv2.ADAPTIVE_THRESH_GAUSSIAN_C,
cv2.THRESH_BINARY,113,11)
```



```
img2Char1 = pytesseract.image_to_string(adaptive_threshold)
img2Char1 = ' '.join(img2Char1.splitlines())
print(img2Char1)
```

KHALED HOSSEINI THE KITE RUNNER

vii. We calculated accuracy of both grayscale image and thresholded image using sequenceMatcher

```
from difflib import SequenceMatcher
sm = SequenceMatcher
acc=sm(None,"KHALED HOSSEINI THE KITE RUNNER",img2Char).ratio()
acc = acc*100
print(round(acc, 2), "%")
```

85.71 %

```
acc=sm(None,"KHALED HOSSEINI THE KITE RUNNER",img2Char1).ratio()
acc1 = acc*100
print(round(acc1, 2), "%")
```

89.19 %

viii. Finally, we considered the text with more accuracy as search text

```
if acc1>acc:
    searchText = img2Char1
else:
    searchText = img2Char
print("The searchable text is",searchText)
```

The searchable text is KHALED HOSSEINI THE KITE RUNNER

VI. RESULT

- When we compare the accuracy of the unprocessed image, we got 46.15 %.
- The gray-scale image has an accuracy of 91.8%
- And finally, after adaptive thresholding, the accuracy was raised to 98.41%

VII. CONCLUSION

Image processing extracts relevant information from an image. Using the image processing algorithm images are fed in different ways to get accurate results. Tesseract-OCR is not accurate in detecting texts from images, especially from colored images. Therefore, images should be pre-processed and grayscaled to get a more accurate result. Compared to other OCR models like Keras-OCR, the tesseract is considered cheap but less efficient. But proper cleaning of data can give you an adequate result.

VIII. REFERENCES

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